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ANALYSING THE ROLE OF BLOCKCHAIN IN BILATERAL TRADE BETWEEN INDIA AND CHINA AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIA'S GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT

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Abstract

This study analyses the impact of India's exports and imports from China on India's Gross Domestic Product and the role of blockchain after digitalization. This study has used secondary data from the World Bank, RBI, and Ministry of Commerce and Industry. The correlation and regression analysis results show that the impact of India's exports and imports from China on the Gross Domestic Product is positive. This study shows that blockchain is playing an important role in India's imports and exports to China. Blockchain simplifies and secures the trade process, promoting transparent and reliable trade dynamics.

Keywords: India-China, Blockchain, Bilateral Trade

Introduction

The global economic landscape is being reshaped by digitalization, making it a disruptive force in various aspects of modern life. This shift will enhance productivity, linkages and creativity through blending digital technology into conventional operations. India and China are the world's two most populous countries have a complicated and significant bilateral commercial connection. These Asian giants' economic relations encompass a wide range of commodities and services, including electronics, manufacturing, textiles, and information technology. They are now important actors in the world economy because of their economic interconnectedness. Despite periodic geopolitical disputes, both nations have made efforts to strengthen their economic connections, seeing the advantages of collaboration. Digitalization has been essential in improving the efficiency and transparency of cross-border transactions between India and China coinciding with the development of their commercial connections. The advent of digital technology has given rise to prospects for e-commerce, supply chain optimisation, and real-time communication have enhanced and broadened their commercial partnership. The rising use of financial technology and digital payment systems has made transactions safer and more seamless by facilitating the transfer of cash. Blockchain is a technical advancement that has gained interest in the context of global trade. In conclusion, Blockchain is a decentralised distributed ledger system that ensures transparent and secure recording as well as verification of transactions. Therefore, blockchain technology is having an impact on the trading activities between India and China while solving trust issues, safety issues, as well as inefficiency problems regarding international trade.

Review of Literature

Arti Yadav and Munir Hassan (2022) in their paper disclosed that China's economy is growing faster than India's, and when comparing international trade with China, India's imports are significantly large, resulting in a trade imbalance. ¹

Moinak Maiti and Prathajit Kayal (2017) examine that Digitalization has had a remarkable impact on the growth rate of India's services sector and MSME segment since 2000. It automates products and processes, increasing quality and production. Digitalization has improved their operating performance, profitability and productivity, contributing significantly to overall trade growth. Digitalization has a high impact on the inclusive growth of the Indian economy and trade. ²

Dr. Asiya Chaudhary and Sabiha Khatoon (2012), analysed that Both countries have had extraordinary progress since being liberated, and bilateral trade between them is expanding quickly. The study in this paper found that China profits greatly and is a significant source of imports for India. ³

Suman Rani (2016) concluded that the Digital India project provides a huge opportunity to use the latest technology to redefine India the paradigms of the service industry. It also pointed out that many

projects may require some transformational process, reengineering, and refinements to achieve the desired service level objectives. ⁴

Dheeraj Badam and Dr. Saikat Gochhait (2020) examine that after the implementation of digitalization, there has been a good impact on the Indian economy. MSME plays an important role in the Indian economy and the usage of smartphones impacted digital transactions and brought transparency and accountability to the financial system. ⁵

Dr. Bhavesh H. Bharad (2016) analysed that Digitalization is the process of converting information into digital formats, transforming human lives and empowering society. India is moving towards a cashless society, using digital systems for security and digital controls. Digitalization has made daily life less dependent and communication more accessible. ⁶

Dr. Binod Kumar (2020) analysed that Digitalization has significantly impacted the Indian economy, creating job opportunities for youth and encouraging startups. The government encourages cashless transactions and adopts digital payments, promoting legality and security. Digital payments also discourage money laundering and terrorism funding, while high-speed internet connectivity and mobile internet connections provide efficient services to citizens. Digital infrastructure, including high-speed internet, is crucial for the country's economic growth. ⁷

I. Ahmedov (2020) examines the impact of digitalization and related technologies on international trade, highlighting the rapid growth of the global economy and the digital space. It highlights the changes in trade structure, competition intensification, digitalization opportunities, cross-border commerce expansion, and reduced operations in a globalized digital environment. Factors like digital commerce, new science, and changes in international trade regulation contribute to the ongoing transformation of international trade. ⁸

Dr. R. Gokilavani and Dr. R. Durgarani (2016) in their study examine Digital India as a struggle in which progress and networks will collide to impact all aspects of governance and improve the quality of life of the general public and the country. It acknowledges the efforts of multiple stakeholders to transform India's economy into a digital economy. ⁹

Dishani Sen (2020) in their study examines the levels of participation and the factors which determine the various aspects of perception and knowledge of this digital economy and digitalization among middle-aged adults in India. They state in their study that rural regions have a negative view of a cashless economy and participation is low owing to accessibility difficulties. Men utilise internet services more to preserve their social position, while women feel left out. ¹⁰

Sara Saberi, Mahtab Kouhizadeh, Joseph Sarkis and Lejia Shen (2018) examine the potential applications of blockchain technology and smart contracts in supply chain management, focusing on how these technologies can help meet sustainability goals. It introduces four categories of barriers to adoption: inter-organizational, intra-organizational, technical, and external. ¹¹

J. Shyla (2020) examines that digital technology is influencing the future of global commerce and investment. The utilisation of automated data exchange platforms, cloud computing, big data, and open-source operating systems can help firms conduct international supply chain management more efficiently. In reality, the application of digital technology in commercial operations can extend beyond online buying and selling. ¹²

Objectives of the Study

1. To provide an overview of bilateral trade between India and China from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022.
2. To examine the impact of India's exports to China on gross domestic product and the role of blockchain after digitalization.
3. To examine the impact of India's imports from China on gross domestic product and the role of blockchain after digitalization.

Hypothesis of study

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of India's exports and imports from China on gross domestic product and the role of blockchain after digitalization.

H11: There is a significant impact of India’s exports and imports from China on gross domestic product and the role of blockchain after digitalization.

Overview of bilateral trade between India and China from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022

India and China are two of the largest and fastest-growing economies in the world. Bilateral trade between these two countries has been growing rapidly over the past few years, but the relationship between the two countries has been marked by tensions, particularly in the political and military spheres. Here is an overview of India and China's bilateral trade from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022:

Trade Volume - In 2015-2016, the total bilateral trade between India and China was US \$ 70.71 billion. In 2019-2020, this figure had risen to US \$ 81.87 billion. However, in 2020-2021, total bilateral trade reached US \$ 86.39 billion and in 2021-2022, the trade volume further increased to US \$ 115.82 billion.

Trade Balance - India has had a significant trade deficit with China in the past few years. In 2015-2016, India's imports from China were worth US \$ 61.70 billion, while its exports to China were worth only US \$ 9.01 billion. This trade imbalance continued to grow over the years, and in 2019-2020, India's imports from China were worth US \$ 65.26 billion, while its exports to China were worth only US \$ 16.61 billion. In 2021 -2022, India’s imports from China were worth US \$ 94.57 billion, while its exports to China were worth US \$ 21.25 billion.

Tensions and Restrictions - The bilateral trade relationship between India and China has been marked by tensions and restrictions. In 2020, India imposed restrictions on the imports of certain Chinese goods, to reduce its dependence on Chinese imports and China also imposed restrictions on Indian products.

Table 1: India’s exports to China from 2015 -2016 to 2021-2022

YEAR	EXPORTS TO CHINA (IN US \$ BILLION)	GROWTH OF EXPORTS (%)
2015-2016	9.01	-24.49
2016-2017	10.17	12.88
2017-2018	13.33	31.08
2018-2019	16.75	25.64
2019-2020	16.61	-0.83
2020-2021	21.18	27.54
2021-2022	21.25	0.34

Source: Ministry of Commerce and Industry

Figure 1: Percentage growth of India’s exports to China

Source: Ministry of Commerce and Industry

From the figure 1, India's exports to China had a mixed growth trend from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022. In 2015-2016, exports stood at US \$ 9.01 billion, experiencing a significant decline of -24.49 %. However, the subsequent years saw a steady recovery. In 2016-2017, exports increased by 12.88%, reaching US \$10.17 billion. The positive momentum continued, with a remarkable growth of 31.08% in 2017-2018, amounting to US \$13.33 billion. The trend persisted in 2018-2019, recording a 25.64% surge to US \$16.75 billion. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is evident in the 2019-2020 data, where exports dropped slightly by -0.83% to US \$16.61 billion. Despite the global challenges posed by the pandemic, the subsequent year, 2020-2021, witnessed a robust recovery with a notable 27.54% growth, reaching US \$ 21.18 billion. The growth continued in 2021-2022, albeit at a more modest rate of 0.34%, totalling \$21.25 billion.

Table 2: India's imports from China from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022

YEAR	IMPORTS FROM CHINA (IN US \$ BILLION)	GROWTH OF IMPORTS (%)
2015-2016	61.70	2.14
2016-2017	61.28	-0.69
2017-2018	76.38	24.64
2018-2019	70.31	-7.94
2019-2020	65.26	-7.19
2020-2021	65.21	-0.07
2021-2022	94.57	45.02

Source: Ministry of Commerce and Industry

Figure 2: Percentage growth of India's imports from China

Source: Ministry of Commerce and Industry

From the figure 2, India's imports from China had a mixed growth trend from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022. In 2015-2016, the imports grew by 2.14% to reach US \$ 61.70 billion, representing a growth rate of 2.14%. In 2016-2017, the imports further decreased by -0.69% to reach US \$ 61.28 billion, representing a decline rate of -0.69%. In 2017-2018, the imports grew significantly by 24.64% to reach US \$ 76.38 billion, representing a growth rate of 24.64%. In 2018-2019, the imports continued to decrease by -7.94% to reach US \$ 70.31 billion, representing a decline rate of -7.94%. In 2019-2020, the imports decreased by -7.19% to reach US \$ 65.26 billion, representing a decline rate of -7.19%. In 2020-2021, the imports declined by -0.07% to reach US \$ 65.21 billion, representing a decline rate of -0.07%. In 2021-2022, imports increased by 45.02% to reach US \$ 94.57 billion, representing growth rate of 45.02%.

Methodology of research

This study aimed to analyse the role of Blockchain in Bilateral Trade Between India and China and its Impact on India's gross domestic product after digitalization. This research is based mainly on secondary data sources. Data and information have been collected from the International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank, World Trade Organization (WTO), Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Ministry of Commerce and Industry, etc. and data from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022 were employed in this study. In this research, Excel Software is used for the calculation and correlation, regression analysis and Anova have been used to examine the impact of imports and exports to China on India's gross domestic product after digitalization and to assess the specific role of Blockchain in shaping these dynamics. This methodological approach aims to provide an in-depth understanding of how Blockchain contributes to the bilateral trade dynamics and impacts India's overall economic performance.

Table 3: Variables used in the study (amount in US \$ BILLION)

YEAR	EXPORTS TO CHINA	IMPORTS FROM CHINA	GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT
2015-2016	9.01	61.70	2290
2016-2017	10.17	61.28	2650
2017-2018	13.33	76.38	2700
2018-2019	16.75	70.31	2840
2019-2020	16.61	65.26	2670
2020-2021	21.18	65.21	3150
2021-2022	21.25	94.57	3420

Source: Ministry of Commerce and Industry, World Bank Database

Table 4: Correlation result of India's exports to China and Gross Domestic Product

	EXPORTS TO CHINA	GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT
EXPORTS TO CHINA	1	0.90507827
GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT	0.90507827	1

Source: Excel output

Table 5: Regression result of India's exports to China and Gross Domestic Product

REGRESSION STATISTICS	
Multiple R	0.90507827
R Square	0.819166675
Adjusted R Square	0.78300001
Standard Error	171.7845509
Observations	7

Independent Variable: Exports to China

Dependent Variable: Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Annual)

Source: Excel output

Table 6: Anova result of India's exports to China and Gross Domestic Product

ANOVA					
	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	668393.1976	668393.1976	22.64977092	0.005063123
Residual	5	147549.6596	29509.93191		
Total	6	815942.8571			

Source: Excel output

Interpretation and Analysis of Impact on India's Export to China on Gross Domestic Product and the role of blockchain after digitalization -

The correlation analysis between India's exports to China and gross domestic product reveals a very highly positive relationship, with a correlation coefficient of 0.90507827. This indicates a very high degree of correlation between the two variables, suggesting that as India's exports to China increase, there is a corresponding rise in the gross domestic product. The coefficient of determination is 0.819166675 explaining approximately 81.91 % of the variance in gross domestic product based on the variations in exports to China. The Adjusted R Square is 0.78300001 which implies that the model's explanatory power remains robust even after considering potential confounding factors. The F-statistic, with a value of 22.64977092, tests the overall significance of the regression model. The Significance F value of 0.005063123 is below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, indicating that the model is statistically significant. This suggests that India's exports to China have a significant impact on the gross domestic product. In conclusion, the results of the correlation analysis and regression model suggest a substantial and statistically significant relationship between India's exports to China and its gross domestic product, highlighting the economic importance of the trade dynamics between these two nations.

Impact of Digitalization in India's Exports to China –

The digitalization wave has brought a significant transformation to India's exports to China. With the rapid adoption of digital technologies, businesses in India have streamlined their operations, enhanced efficiency, and expanded their reach. E-commerce platforms have played a pivotal role, providing Indian exporters with direct access to the vast Chinese consumer market. This has resulted in a notable increase in export volumes, as digital platforms facilitate easier trade transactions and bridge the geographical gap. Additionally, the use of digital tools has improved communication, reduced transaction costs, and increased transparency in the supply chain, fostering a more conducive environment for trade between India and China. Overall, the impact of digitalization on India's exports to China has been substantial, opening up new avenues for economic growth and collaboration between the two nations.

Role of Blockchain in India's Exports to China –

Blockchain technology has played a significant role in reshaping India's exports to China. Its implementation has introduced a new level of transparency, security, and efficiency in the trade ecosystem. By utilising blockchain, the entire supply chain process, from manufacturing to shipment, gains an immutable and transparent ledger that all relevant parties can access. This not only reduces the risk of fraud and errors but also ensures real-time visibility into the status and location of goods. In the context of India and China trade, blockchain facilitates a trustworthy and decentralised platform for transactions, minimizing the need for intermediaries and expediting cross-border payments. Smart contracts, a key feature of blockchain, automate and enforce contractual agreements, further streamlining the export process. Ultimately, blockchain has emerged as a transformative force, enhancing the reliability and efficiency of India's exports to China while fostering a more secure and seamless trading environment.

Table 7: Correlation result of India's Imports from China and Gross Domestic Product

	IMPORTS FROM CHINA	GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT
IMPORTS FROM CHINA	1	0.7296743
GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT	0.7296743	1

Source: Excel output

Table 8: Regression result of India's Imports from China and Gross Domestic Product

REGRESSION STATISTICS	
Multiple R	0.7296743
R Square	0.532424584
Adjusted R Square	0.4389095
Standard Error	276.2299119
Observations	7

Independent Variable: Imports from China

Dependent Variable: Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Annual)

Source: Excel output

Table 9: Anova result of India's Imports from China and Gross Domestic Product

ANOVA					
	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	434428.0359	434428.0359	5.693462112	0.062689776
Residual	5	381514.8212	76302.96424		
Total	6	815942.8571			

Source: Excel output

Interpretation and Analysis of Impact on India's Imports from China on Gross Domestic Product and the role of blockchain after digitalization -

The correlation analysis between India's imports from China and gross domestic product reveals a moderately positive relationship, with a correlation coefficient of 0.7296743. This indicates a moderate degree of correlation between the two variables, suggesting that as India's imports to China increase, there is a corresponding rise in the gross domestic product. The coefficient of determination (R square) is 0.532424584 explaining approximately 53.24 % of the variance in gross domestic product based on the variations in imports to China. The Adjusted R Square is 0.4389095 which implies that the model's explanatory power remains robust even after considering potential confounding factors. The F-statistic, with a value of 5.693462112, tests the overall significance of the regression model. The Significance F value of 0.062689776 is more than the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, which indicates that India's imports from China have no significant impact on the gross domestic product.

Impact of Digitalization on India's Imports from China -

Digitalization has significantly influenced India's imports from China by fostering a shift in sourcing strategies and supply chain dynamics. The rise of e-commerce platforms has empowered Indian businesses to explore alternative suppliers globally, reducing their reliance on traditional intermediaries and facilitating direct connections with manufacturers. The optimization of supply chain processes through digital technologies has enhanced efficiency, reducing dependence on any single country. Moreover, the ease of cross-border trade enabled by digital platforms has opened avenues for diversification, allowing businesses to explore suppliers beyond China. Digital tools have streamlined customs procedures and trade facilitation, while innovations and changing consumer preferences driven by digitalization contribute to a re-evaluation of import patterns. This transformative impact is instrumental in shaping a more dynamic and diversified landscape for India's imports, diminishing the singular focus on Chinese markets.

Role of Blockchain in India's Imports from China -

Blockchain technology can play a transformative role in India's imports from China by enhancing the efficiency, transparency, and security of the supply chain. Through its decentralised and immutable

ledger, blockchain enables a transparent and traceable record of transactions, reducing the risk of fraud and counterfeiting in the import process. Smart contracts can automate trade agreements, streamlining customs processes and expediting payments. The technology's cryptographic features ensure data security, vital for the sensitive information exchanged in international trade. By fostering trust among stakeholders and providing a reliable platform for transactions, blockchain has the potential to streamline import and export operations, reduce paperwork, and facilitate faster, more secure cross-border transactions, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and efficient trade relationship between India and China.

Conclusion-

This paper has tried to analyse the impact of India's exports and imports from China on gross domestic product and the role of blockchain after digitalization. According to the statistical analysis, the correlation between India's exports to China and gross domestic product reveals a very highly positive relationship indicated by the correlation coefficient of 0.90507827. The value of R Square is 0.819166675 suggests that approximately 81.91% of the variability in gross domestic product can be explained by the variations in India's exports to China. The value of Adjusted R Square is 0.78300001 which accounts for the number of predictors in the model, reinforcing the robustness of the relationship. The value of F is 22.64977092 which is statistically significant with a value of significance F is 0.005063123 which supports the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant impact of India's exports to China on the gross domestic product. The correlation between India's imports from China and gross domestic product is moderately positive with a correlation coefficient of 0.7296742. The value of R Square value is 0.532424584 which indicates that approximately 53.24 % of the variability in gross domestic product can be explained by the variations in India's imports from China. The value of F is 5.693462112 which is statistically significant with a value of significance F is 0.062689776 which supports the rejection of the alternative hypothesis. Therefore, the null hypothesis is validated, suggesting no significant impact of India's imports from China on the gross domestic product.

After reviewing the research paper, it is revealed that researchers conducted a study on the impact of digitalization and the role of blockchain in various aspects. Some researchers have seen the social impact of digitalization while others looked at economic effects on India's Digital India and how rural and urban residents contribute to this country's digital economy. The researchers studied how digitalization has affected the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector as well as foreign direct investment. It was noted from reviewing the research paper that the researcher researched globalisation's impact on international business specifically on supply chain and cross-border trade. Reviewing literature shows that researchers have been studying global digitalization and blockchain in global trading but no one studied it from the perspective of bilateral trade between India and China when they discussed the impact of digitalisation as well as the role of blockchain in global trade. In my paper, I studied the impact of India's exports and imports from China on Gross Domestic Product, as well as the role of blockchain in bilateral trade, using data from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022. This study also has some limitations, I have worked on imports and exports to China in this paper but did not focus on the trade deficit, Foreign Direct Investment, and the growth rate of gross domestic product. In this study, I focused on the impact of India's exports and imports from China on the Gross Domestic Product and the role of blockchain. But in future, we can study the impact of India's exports and imports from China and the role of blockchain on Foreign Direct Investment, the growth rate of gross domestic product and the trade deficit of different countries.

Blockchain is a technology that creates a decentralised and secure ledger, ensuring transparency and security of transactions. After adopting blockchain technology, India and China are improving product traceability, reducing fraud risks and streamlining the entire supply chain process. Due to blockchain paperwork, customs clearance and compliance are being streamlined. Digitalization has been transformative for India's exports and imports from China, increasing efficiency and competitiveness. The application of blockchain technology allows for a secure and transparent trading environment. In

this era where global economic dynamics are rapidly changing, it is important to embrace such advancements in technology for sustainable economic growth.

In conclusion, Blockchain creates a decentralised and secure ledger that ensures transparent transactions. After implementing blockchain, India and China are increasing product traceability, reducing the risk of fraud and streamlining the entire supply chain process. Digitalization has transformed India's exports and imports from China making it more efficient and competitive. Therefore, there should be integration between blockchain technology with trade frameworks to enhance secure trade relationships.

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